

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Management of Knowledge application through Community Service and Institutional Effectiveness in Colleges of Education in South-South Zone, Nigeria

Udo David Ekpenyong ^{1,3,*}, Ekwere Mercy Robert ^{2,3} and Udo Esuabanga Ekanem ^{1,3}

¹ Department of Educational Foundations, School of Education, Nigeria.

² Department of Chemistry, School of Science, Nigeria.

³ Cross River State College of Education, Akamkpa- Nigeria.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(01), 1319–1324

Publication history: Received on 04 June 2024; revised on 14 July 2024; accepted on 17 July 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.1.2102>

Abstract

Institutional effectiveness refers to the ongoing process through which an institution measures its performance against its stated mission and goals for the purpose of evaluation and improvement. Knowledge application through Community service by Lecturers to enhance their Institutional effectiveness in College of Education was investigated. This mandate is usually neglected by the Lecturers. A survey design was adopted for the study and census sampling technique was used because the population of Heads of Departments from four Colleges Education in South-South Zone, Nigeria was small. Knowledge Application Through Community Service and Institutional Effectiveness Questionnaire (KATCSIEQ), a researcher constructed instrument was used to obtained data from the subjects and independent t-test was used to analyzed the data. The results show among others that; there is significant difference between knowledge application through Community service and institutional effectiveness in College of Education. It was therefore recommended that researchers and Management of Institutions should encourage the use of Community service to enhance institutional effectiveness in College of Education.

Keywords: Application; Community Service; Colleges; Institutional Effectiveness; Knowledge

1. Introduction

Institutional effectiveness refers to the ongoing process through which an Institution measures its performance against its stated mission and goals for the purpose of evaluation and improvement. Institutional effectiveness has moved to the forefront of the dialogue among government agencies, accrediting organizations and higher administrator.

In this age of ever-increasing pressure for accountability, students, parents, government officials and accrediting agencies are demanding responsiveness from Institution of higher education (Welsh & Metalf, 2003).

Institutional effectiveness is the systematic, explicit and documented process of measuring performance against mission in all aspects of an Institution (Emory Resource Manual, 2013). Institutions of higher learning are measured in terms of purpose, objectives consistent with mission, documentation of students' achievement, intended outcomes, global accomplishment and regular evaluation of students' outcomes and it is used in improvement of educational programmes (Nicolas and Nichole in Anumaka, 2013). Institutional effectiveness is a developmental process which allows measures.

* Corresponding author: Udo David Ekpenyong

A planned assessment process that are purposely linked to institutional goals promote attention to those goals and plans towards ensuring that outcomes are sound and not disappointing (Middle States Commission on Higher Education, 2005).

Tertiary institutions (College of Education inclusive) have always had as their fundamental objectives, the pursuit of triple mandate of knowledge (or research function), knowledge transmission (or teaching function), knowledge application (or Community services), (Udo, 2019). Therefore, knowledge application through Community service by lecturers to enhance their Institution effectiveness in terms of students' evaluation is the focus of the study and the problem of the study is centred on why the mandate is usually neglected by lecturers and may be constituting problem of institutional effectiveness within the framework of College Education in South-South Zone, Nigeria.

According to (Perold and Omar, 1997) knowledge application in Community service is defined in broad term, as programmes linked to higher education that involve participation activities designed to deliver social benefits to a particular Community in ways that teach the participants to work jointly towards achieving the common goal. Participation in Community service usually involves a degree of personal service in terms of time, remuneration and convenient. In some cases, lecturers can benefit through research publication. Therefore, Institutions (College of Education) discover how effective they are by assessing teaching, research and Community service.

(Usoro, 2011) sees Community service as an act performed by caring individuals who wants to contribute to the betterment of their Community. It connotes reward whether in cash or kind. Through Community service people are linked to wider Community and exposed to others and situations outside their everyday experiences.

(Ehigiamusoe, 2012) asserted that continuous and holistic improvement in College of Education system requires the collaborative efforts of various stakeholders both internal and external; he added that collaboration will help to trigger improvement in the higher education system.

(Chuku, Owan and Aduma, 2023) found out in their study that institutional leadership significantly influenced research productivity and Community service engagement among academic staff.

(Dumn, 2022) revealed that students received first hand exposure to community service within their own community and results showed improvement in their grades and classroom behavior which leads to institutional effectiveness.

(Oyekan, 2013) opined that effective synergy with Community service will help to protect and enhance societal values by training young people through preparatory class in the values which form the basis of democratic citizenship and by providing critical perspective to assist in the improvement or effectiveness of the Institution.

(Oyerinde in Chuku, Owan and Aduma, 2023) found out that among others, preparatory class and work environment among other factors was a major factor contributing to low institutional effectiveness in Polytechnics in South Western Nigeria. Preparatory class is usually private school preparing students primarily for College. It is serving to prepare and so lecturers do take part as their Community service contribution to ensure their fulfillment of that mandate.

(Anumaka, 2013) deduced from her study that research in higher education is not given priority and research findings or results are not usually referenced for quality decision making by the concerned authority. Research is an essential function of higher education Institution and seems must crucial amongst the identified functions Higher Education, namely; teaching, research, Community service, and storage of information. Findings has revealed that gap exist between research and utilization of findings in most Institution.

According to (Tibenderand, 2013) teaching cannot be separated from research as University academics and research are positively correlated.

(Anumaka, 2018) stated that research findings in higher education are only in context of academic study. This context does not make findings readily useable for organizations to transfer these findings into usable form. (Anumaka, 2013) formed that lack of advocacy or promotion of current research findings to the public for reference purposes and quality decision making is one of the factors influencing the utilization of research findings in the universities.

(Oyedeji and Oyebanji, 2021) find out that funding was the highest contributor to institutional effectiveness in College of Education, Ilesa, Osan Skelep Nigeria ($B = 0.682$; $t = 3.439$; $p < 0.005$).

1.1. Hypothesis

- **HO₁:** There is no significant difference between knowledge application through Community service and institutional effectiveness in College of Education.
- **HO₂:** There is no significant difference between the preparatory class and institutional effectiveness in College of Education.
- **HO₃:** There is no significant difference between research findings and institutional effectiveness in College of Education.

2. Methodology

Tertiary Institutions worldwide (College of Education inclusive), have always had as their fundamental objectives, the pursuit of triple mandate of knowledge generation (or research function), knowledge transmission (or teaching function) knowledge application (or Community Services). It could be said that knowledge transmission in the first among equal of the functions of College of Education system because teaching is the first task of the lecturer although the three functions are interrelated and can be hardly be divorced from one another (Umar, 2011).

Therefore, knowledge application through Community service by lecturers to enhance their institutional effectiveness in terms of students evaluation, goal accomplishment and effective Community is the focus of this study and the problem of the study is centered on why this mandate is usually neglected by lecturers and may be constituting part of the problem of institutional effectiveness within the framework of College of Education, Lecturer are at the focus of any human resources development and also the major agent through which the curriculum of education funds it fulfillment and actualization.

Therefore, for the objective of education of any nation to be realized, it is obvious to translate the educational objectives and philosophy at any level into reality. It is against this background that the researchers designed this work to determine knowledge application through services and their institutional effectiveness in terms of student evaluation, goal accomplishment and effective communication and find out any other factors that can enhance productivity generally in College of Education system.

A survey design was adopted for the study. This is to enable the researchers to determine significant of difference of scores of Heads of Departments concerning lecturers' knowledge application through Community service and institutional effectiveness in four Colleges of Education in South-South Zone of Nigeria. Four (4) samples Colleges of Education in the South-South Zone of Nigeria – Cross River State, Akwa Ibom State, Rivers State, Bayelsa State. Heads of Departments (HODs) from the Colleges of Education were selected for the study. Census sampling technique was used considering the few number of the population. All the HODs in the Colleges served as the population and also both male and female HODs were used for the study.

Data collection was carried out with the use of a constructed instrument called Knowledge Application through Community Service and Institutional Effectiveness Questionnaire (KATCSIEQ). The instrument was face validated by experts in measurement and evaluation and had reliability coefficient estimates of 0.63 to 0.85, figures which confirmed that the instrument was reliable enough for the successful realization of the study objectives.

The researchers administered the instrument to 200 HODs. This measure ensured a 100 percent return rate. Independent t-test analysis was used in data analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Hypothesis

3.1.1. HO₁: There is no significant difference between knowledge application through Community service and institutional effectiveness.

Table 1 Summary data of independent t-test of knowledge application through community service and institutional effectiveness

S/N	Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	D.F	$t_{cal.}$	Sign
1	Knowledge application	200	14.70	2.84			
					198	2.30	0.02
2	Institutional effectiveness	200	68.28	7.41			

$P < .05$ $t = (198)$ critical = 1.65

From table 1, since the calculated independent test is 2.30 which is greater than the critical value of the independent t-test of 1.65 at .05 level of significance for 198 degree of freedom, it implies that the null hypothesis of “no significant difference” was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was retained. Therefore, there is significant difference between knowledge application through Community service and institutional effectiveness in College of Education.

3.2. Hypothesis 2

3.2.1. H_{02} : There is no significant difference between the preparatory class and institutional effectiveness in Colleges of Education.

Table 2 Summary data of independent t-test of the preparatory class and institution effectiveness in Colleges of Education

S/N	Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	D.F	$t_{cal.}$	Sign
1	Preparatory class	200	16.91	3.17			
					198	0.70	0.49
2	Institutional effectiveness	200	68.28	7.41			

$P < .05$ $t = (198)$ critical = 1.65

From table 2, since the independent t-test calculated of 0.70 is less than the critical independent t-test of 1.65 at .05 level of significance for 198 degree of freedom for a two tailed test. It therefore, implies that the null hypothesis of “no significant difference” is retained or not rejected while the alternative null hypothesis was rejected. It means that there is no significant difference between preparatory class and institutional effectiveness in College of Education.

3.2.2. H_{03} : There is no significant difference between research findings and institutional effectiveness through community service in college of education.

Table 3 Summary data of independent t-test of research findings and institution effectiveness in Colleges of Education

S/N	Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	D.F	$t_{cal.}$	Sign
1	Research findings	200	13.70	1.54			
					198	0.69	0.95
2	Institutional effectiveness	200	62.28	6.83			

$P < .05$ $t (198)$ critical = 1.65

From table 3, show a t-test calculated independent t-test of .69 which is less than the critical value of independent t-test of 1.65 at .05 level of significance for 198 degree of freedom for a two tailed test. This implies that the null hypothesis of “no significance difference” is retained or not rejected and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. It means that there is no significant difference between research findings and institutional effectiveness in College of Education.

4. Discussion

The discussion of findings was done by null hypothesis as stated below: The first result of the first null hypothesis shows that there is significant difference between knowledge application through community service and institutional effectiveness in Colleges of Education.

This findings is in collaboration with some authors like (Usoro, 2011), (Ehigiamoze, 2012) who asserted that continuous and holistic improvement in Colleges of Education system require collaboration of stakeholders which will trigger effectiveness in the institution. The study of Dunn (2020) was also in agreement. The finding disagreed with (Chuku, Owan and Aduma, 2023). The difference in the present work and other past study may be due to geographical location and sample size.

The result of the second null hypothesis shows that there is no significant difference between preparatory class and institutional effectiveness in College of Education. The finding is in disagreement with (Oyerinde in Chuktu, Owan and Aduma 2023) who found out that preparatory class and work environment among other factors was a major factors contributing in low institutional effectiveness of Polytechnic in South Western Nigeria.

The findings is in line with (Oyekan, 2013) who opined that an effective synergy with community services will help to protect and enhance societal values by training young people through preparatory class in the value which form the basis of democratic citizenship and by providing critical perspectives to assist in the improvement effectiveness of institution.

The third result of the finding showed that there is no significant difference between research findings and institutional effectiveness in College of Education.

This finding is in line with (Anumaka, 2013) who deduced from her study that gaps exist between research and utilization of findings in most institutions which could affect institution effectiveness negatively. The finding was not congruous with that of (Oyededeji and Oyebanyi, 2021) who revealed in their study that funding was the highest contributor to institutional effectiveness in College of Education.

5. Conclusion

On the strength of the findings, these conclusions were drawn. There is significant difference between knowledge application through Community service and institutional effectiveness in Colleges of Education. There is no significant difference between preparatory class and institutional effectiveness in Colleges of Education and there is no significant difference between research findings and institutional effectiveness in College of Education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- Researchers, institutional management should encourage the use of knowledge application through community service to enhance institutional effectiveness.
 - Stakeholders in Educational industry mostly the management should avoid the use of a single factor (variable) through community service to determine the institutional effectiveness of college of education.
 - Federal government should increase research finding grant in order to enhance good research findings and utilization and productiveness in College of education.
-

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Anumaka, R. B. (2013). Institutional effectiveness: Best practices and assessment strategies in Ugandan Universities. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 3(2), 20-24.

- [2] Chuku, O. Owan, V. J., Aduma, P. O. (2023). Institutional variables as antecedents of academic staff teaching, research productivity and community service in Universities. International Conference on Research Conference, Praque, Czech Republic.
- [3] Dunn, J. (2020). Community Service in the classroom setting: A research study. Retrieved on April, 2024 from, <http://digital/commons.assumption.edu/honourstheories>.
- [4] Ehigiamusoe, U. K. (2012). Private sector participation in secondary education: Implication for national development. *International Journal of Development*. 4(2), 30-35.
- [5] Middle State' Commission on higher education (2005). www.middlestatecommisison.org.
- [6] Oyedeji, A. & Oyebanyi, O. J. (2021). Labour Unionism and institutional effectiveness in Osun State College of Education, Ilesa, Osun State, Nigeria. Retrieved on 10th April, 2024 from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/353688225>.
- [7] Oyekan, O. A. (2013). Benchmarking periodic review minimum standard and exchange programme for staff and students as predictors of quality of graduates in Nigerian Public Universities. *Journal of Education Policy Review* 5(2), 60-63.
- [8] Perold, H. & Omar, R. (1997). *Community service in higher Education: A concept paper*. Pretoria: Joint Education of South Africa.
- [9] Tiberderand, P. K. (2013). *Modernization of University and Education in Uganda: Prescription for progress*. Kampala: Makere University Printery.
- [10] Uboro, E. B. (2011). *Functions of the University*. In S. U. Bassey, U. U. Bassey (Eds.). *Management of Higher Education in Africa*. Uyo: Abaam Publishing Company.
- [11] Udo, D. E. (2019). University mandate, quality assurance and institutional effectiveness in Universities in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States, Nigeria. Unpublished PhD dissertation of University of Calabar.
- [12] Umar, A. M. (2011). Impediments to qualitative education in tertiary institutions of learning: A religion teaching perspective. *Nigeria Journal of Teachers Education and Teaching*. 9(1), 2019-226.
- [13] Welsh, J. F. & Metcalf, J. (2003). Faculty and administrative support for institutional effectiveness activities. A bridge across the chasm? *Journal of Higher Education*, 74(4), 44568.